

QUALITY CONTROL PARAMETERS AND SAFETY PROFILE OF SIDDHA HERBAL FORMULATION – THALISAPATHIRI VADAGAM

Sripriya S.^{1*}, Venkadesan N.², Essakky Pandian G.³

*¹PG Scholar, Department of PG Gunapadam, Government Siddha Medical College,
Palayamkottai, Tirunelveli.

²PG Scholar, Department of PG Gunapadam, Government Siddha Medical College,
Palayamkottai, Tirunelveli.

³Professor, Head of The Department, Department of PG Gunapadam, Government Siddha
Medical College, Palayamkottai, Tirunelveli.

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*Corresponding Author

Sripriya S.

PG Scholar, Department of PG
Gunapadam, Government Siddha
Medical College, Palayamkottai,
Tirunelveli.

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INTRODUCTION

Siddha medicine is a traditional system of medicine that has been practiced for centuries in South India, especially in Tamil Nadu, and continues to be followed to this day. Siddha medicine developed by Siddhars. Thalishapathiri vadagam is one of the herbal formulations in Siddha medicine prescribed for many diseases like kalladaippu (renal calculi), neer adaippu, piramegm (urinary tract infection). Thalishapathiri vadagam comprises a blend of fifteen ingredients which includes thalishapathiri, adhimadhuram, lavangapattai, thiri kadugu, vaal milagu. These ingredients have lithotriptic, diuretic, antioxidant, antimicrobial, and antispasmodic properties. It is important to assess Thalishapathiri vadagam for physicochemical properties, aflatoxin contamination and microbial load. Such evaluations are essential to ensure the formulation's safety, stability and therapeutic efficacy aligning with pharmacopeial standards.

OBJECTIVES

Aim of the study is to evaluate the quality control parameters and safety profile of the thalishapathiri vadagam by assessing its physicochemical characters, aflatoxin contamination

and microbial load in accordance with pharmacopeial guidelines to ensure its safety and therapeutic reliability.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Thalisapathiri vadagam is a polyherbal siddha formulation mentioned in siddha literature Sarabenthira Vaithiya Muraigal.

Ingredients

1. *Thalisapathiri*(*Abies spectabilis*) - 1 palam(35 gm)
2. *Nellimulli*(*Phyllanthus emblica*) -1/2 palam (17.5 gm)
3. *Kadukai thol* (*Terminalia chebula*) -1/2 palam(17.5 gm)
4. *Thandrikaithol* (*Terminalia bellirica*) - 1/2 palam 17.5 gm)
5. *Sevviyam*(*Piper nigrum*) - 1/4 palam (8.75 gm)
6. *Vaal milagu*(*Piper cubeba*) - 1/4 palam (8.75 gm)
7. *Lavangapattai*(*Cinnomomum verum*) -1/4 palam (8.75 gm)
8. *Milagu*(*Piper nigrum*) -1/4 palam (8.75 gm)
9. *Adhimadhuram*(*Glycyrrhiza glabra*) -1/4 palam (8.75 gm)
10. *Koshtam*(*Costus speciosus*) -1/4 palam (8.75 gm)
11. *Thippili*(*Piper longum*) - 1/4 palam (8.75 gm)
12. *Jadhikkai*(*Myristica fragrance*) -1 palam (35 gm)
13. *Elam*(*Elettaria cardamomum*) -1/4 palam(8.75 gm)
14. *Seenthil sarkarai*(*Tinospora cordifolia*) -2 palam (70 gm)
15. *Sugar*(*Saccharum officinarum*) -3 palam (105 gm)

Authentication of raw drugs

The identification of herbal drugs are authenticated by experts of gunapadam department govt. siddha medical college palayamkottai.

Preparation of Thaliasapathiri vadagam

Each of the purified raw drugs is ground into a fine powder and combine completely. 5.37 liters of cow's milk were thoroughly heated till they reached a colloidal consistency. To achieve the desired consistency, add 105 grams of sugar and the powdered drugs, stirring thoroughly. After cooling, shape it into a nellikai urundai and dried in shade.

- **Shelf Life**

3 Months

- **Dosage**

Nellikai alavu

- **Indication**

Kalladaippu (Renal Calculi), Neeradaippu, Piramegam, Vayitru pun, Sivanthu neer irangal, Thurmamaisam.

The prepared sample medicine thalisapathiri vadagam subjected to analyzing parameters in global research solution lab, chennai.

Physiochemical analysis

Percentage Loss on Drying

Test drug was accurately weighed in evaporating dish. The sample was dried at 105°C for 5 hours and then weighed.

Determination of Total Ash

Test drug was accurately weighed in silica dish and incinerated at the furnace a temperature 400 °C until it turns white in color which indicates absence of carbon. Percentage of total ash will be calculated with reference to the weight of air-dried drug.

Determination of Acid Insoluble Ash

The ash obtained by total ash test will be boiled with 25 ml of dilute hydrochloric acid for 6mins. Then the insoluble matter is collected in crucible and will be washed with hot water and ignited to constant weight. Percentage of acid insoluble ash will be calculated with reference to the weight of air-dried ash.

Determination of Alcohol Soluble Extractive

Test sample was macerated with 100 ml of Alcohol in a closed flask for twenty-four hours, shaking frequently during six hours and allowing it to stand for eighteen hours. Filter rapidly, taking precautions against loss of solvent, evaporate 25 ml of the filtrate to dryness in a tared flat bottomed shallow dish, and dry at 105°C, to constant weight and weigh. Calculate the percentage of alcohol-soluble extractive with reference to the air-dried drug.

Determination of Water Soluble Extractive

Test sample was macerated with 100 ml of chloroform water in a closed flask for twenty-four hours, shaking frequently during six hours and allowing it to stand and for eighteen hours. Filter rapidly, taking precautions against loss of solvent, evaporate 25 ml of the filtrate to dryness in a tared flat bottomed shallow dish, and dry at 105°C, to constant weight and weigh. Calculate the percentage of water-soluble extractive with reference to the air-dried drug.

pH determination

Required quantity of test sample was admixed with distilled water and the subjected to screening using pH meter.

Aflatoxin assay**Standard**

Aflatoxin B1

Aflatoxin B2

Aflatoxin G1

Aflatoxin G2

Solvent

Standard samples were dissolved in a mixture of chloroform and acetonitrile(9.8:0.2) to obtain a solution having concentrations of 0.5 µg in per ml each of aflatoxin B1 and aflatoxin G1 and 0.1 µg per ml each of aflatoxin B2 and aflatoxin G2.

Procedure

Standard aflatoxin was applied on to the surface to pre coated TLC plate in the volume of 2.5 µL, 5 µL, 7.5 µL and 10 µL. Similarly, the test sample was placed and Allow the spots to dry and develop the chromatogram in an unsaturated chamber containing a solvent system consisting of a mixture of chloroform, acetone and isopropyl alcohol (85:10: 5) until the solvent front has moved not less than 15 cm from the origin. Remove the plate from the developing chamber, mark the solvent front and allow the plate to air-dry. LocatethespotsontheplatebyexaminationunderUVlightat365nm.

STERILITY TEST BY POUR PLATE METHOD

OBJECTIVE

The pour plate techniques were adopted to determine the sterility of the product. Contaminated / un sterile sample (formulation) when come in contact with the nutrition rich medium it promotes the growth of the organism and after stipulated period of incubation the growth of the organism was identified by characteristic pattern of colonies. The colonies are referred to as Colony Forming Units (CFUs).

METHODOLOGY

Test sample was inoculated in sterile petri dish to which about 15 mL of molten agar 45°C were added. Agar and sample were mixed thoroughly by tilting and swirling the dish. Agar was allowed to completely gel without disturbing it. (about 10 minutes). Plates were then inverted and incubated at 37° C for 24-48 hours and further extended for 72 hrs for fungal growth observation. Grown colonies of organism was then counted and calculated for CFU.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

PHYSIOCHEMICAL PARAMETERS;

Table 01.

State	Solid
Nature	Hard Solid with smooth surface
Odor	Characteristic
Touch / Consistency	Rigid
Flow Property	Free flowing
Appearance	Brownish

SOLUBILITY PROFILE

Table 02.

S.No	Solvent Used	Solubility / Dispensability
1	Chloroform	Insoluble
2	Ethanol	Soluble
3	Water	Soluble
4	Ethyl acetate	Insoluble
5	DMSO	Soluble

FINAL TEST REPORTS

Table 03.

S.No	Parameter	Mean (n=3) SD
1.	Loss on Drying at 105 °C (%)	3.867 ± 0.32
2.	Total Ash (%)	1.76 ± 0.30

3.	<i>Acid insoluble Ash (%)</i>	0 ± 0
4.	<i>Water soluble Extractive (%)</i>	13.53 ± 0.92
5.	<i>Alcohol Soluble Extractive (%)</i>	8.1 ± 0.45
6.	<i>Ph</i>	6.6

AFLATOXIN ASSAY

Table 04.

Aflatoxin	SampleTV	AYUSH Specification Limit
B1	Not Detected-Absent	0.5ppm(0.5mg/kg)
B2	Not Detected-Absent	0.1ppm(0.1mg/kg)
G1	Not Detected-Absent	0.5ppm(0.5mg/kg)
G2	Not Detected-Absent	0.1ppm(0.1mg/kg)

The results shown that there were no spots were being identified in the test sample loaded on TLC plates when compare to the standard which indicates that the sample were free from Aflatoxin B1, Aflatoxin B2, Aflatoxin G1 and Aflatoxin G2.

MICROBIAL LOAD DETERMINATION

IMAGE 01. no growth/ colonies was observed in any plates inocuates with the test sample.

OBSERVATION

No growth was observed after incubation period reveals the absence of specific pathogen.

Table 05.

Test	Result	Specification	As per AYUSH/WHO
<i>Total Bacterial Count</i>	Absent	NMT 10 ⁵ CFU/g	As per AYUSH specification
<i>Total Fungal Count</i>	Absent	NMT 10 ³ CFU/g	

DISCUSSION

This study evaluated the quality and safety profile of Thalispapthiri vadagam a siddha formulation, through comprehensive physicochemical, aflatoxin analysis and microbial load

determination. The organoleptic characters of this formulation are brownish in appearance, solid state, hard solid with smooth surface and soluble in water and ethanol. The physicochemical evaluation revealed acceptable values for loss on drying, total ash, acid insoluble ash, and extractive values. These parameters play an important role in determining the stability and purity of herbal formulation. The aflatoxin analysis reveals the absence of detectable levels of B1, B2, G3, G2. Aflatoxin are highly toxic metabolites produced by *Aspergillus* species and are frequently implicated in food and herbal drugs contamination in our country. The absence of aflatoxin contamination in thalisapathiri vadagam highlights the effectiveness of proper storage and processing techniques employed in its preparation. Microbial quality testing reveals that the total bacteria and fungal counts were within WHO acceptable limits. Ensuring microbial safety is essential for formulations intended for internal uses. The low microbial load observed here indicates adherence to good manufacturing practices during preparation. Overall, the study highlights the importance of integrating modern quality control parameters with traditional knowledge to ensure the safety, efficacy and standardization of siddha formulations.

CONCLUSION

The standardization of Thalispapathiri vadagam through Physicochemical, aflatoxin analysis and Microbial count analysis confirmed its safety and quality in accordance with WHO guidelines. These findings validate the purity and safety of thalisapathiri vadagam and support its use as a standardized siddha formulation. Further pharmacological and clinical investigations are recommended to substantiate its therapeutic efficacy.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

No conflict of interest.

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